

EFFECTS OF ORGANIC MANURE AND SPACING ON MARKETABLE AND UNMARKETABLE FRUITS OF TOMATO (*Solanum lycopersicum L.*) IN YOLA, ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* (L.)) is an important vegetable and cheap source of vitamin C, thus ranks number one in contribution to diet. It is widely grown in many tropical areas of the world including Nigeria. However, average yield as obtained by the local farmers in Nigeria has been low, due mainly to lack of adequate information on the spacing and incorporation of poultry manure for optimal yield. Field experiment was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the Department of Crop Production and Horticulture, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria, in the cropping seasons of 2021, 2022 and 2023 to evaluate the effects of Spacing and poultry manure levels on growth and yield Parameters of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* (L)). The treatment consisted of five poultry manure levels (0 tons/ha, 15 tons/ha, 20 tons/ha, 25 tons/ha and 30 tons/ha) as the main plot treatments and five spacing intervals (90x60 cm, 80x40 cm, 60x30 cm, 50x50 cm and 40x20 cm) as sub-plot treatments. The experiment was laid on a split plot design and was replicated three times. Three Tomato cultivars (Tandino, UTC and Dansiriya) were used. Appropriate agronomic practices recommended for the production of tomato were carried out to ensure optimum performance. The parameters measured were number of marketable fruits and number of unmarketable fruits. The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance and significantly different means were separated using Least Significant Difference (LSD). The result showed that 30tons/ha poultry manure significantly affected number of marketable fruits (23.867). Plant spaced 60 x 30cm performed better on number of marketable fruits. Tandino cultivar significantly affected the number of marketable fruits. It is therefore recommended that farmers should plant Tandino cultivar and applied 30 tons/ha rate of poultry manure as well as spacing tomato 60 x30cm for optimum marketable fruits of Tomato in the study area.

Keywords: Marketable Fruits, Unmarketable Fruits, Poultry Manure, Plant, Spacing, Yield Parameters, Growth Parameters

INTRODUCTION

Tomato belongs to the kingdom Plantae, the family Solanaceae and the genus, Solanum. Its botanical name is *Solanum lycopersicum* (L) (Ohlson, et al., 2018). The word “tomato” may refer to the plant or the edible, typically red, fruit that it bears. Tomato originated in America, and was spread around the world following the Spanish colonization of the Americas. It was reported that Tomato was domesticated in Mexico and that the name of Tomato was derived from the word “tomatillo” in the Nahua dialect of Mexico (Ara et al., 2007) and it many varieties are now widely grown, often in greenhouses in cooler climates. Tomato is consumed in diverse ways, including raw, as an ingredient in many dishes and sausages, and drinks. While it is botanically a fruit, it is considered a vegetable for culinary purposes. The fruit is rich in

lycopene which may have beneficial health effects (Ud Din, 2023; Jeffrey, 2013). The plant belongs to the nightshade family, typically grow to 1–3 meters (3–10 ft.) high with a weak stem that often sprawls over the ground and vines over other plants (Jeffrey, 2013).

In terms of production the most leading tomato producing countries in the world are China, India, USA and Turkey with a production of 56.4, 19.4, 12.6 and 12.2 million tons respectively. Egypt has a total annual production of 8.625 million tons and is the highest producer in Africa while Nigeria is the second producer with a total annual production of 1.560 million tones (El-Shafie 2020, FAO, 2014,)

Tomato is popular for its medicinal value. It is also a major component in the daily diet, and can be used in making soups, pickles, ketchup, sauces, juices etc. Ripe tomatoes having antioxidant-lycopene. The well ripped tomato (edible portion/100g) contains water (94.1%); energy (23 calories); Ca (1.0 gm); Mg (7.0 mg); vitamin A (1000 IU); ascorbic acid (22 mg); thiamin (0.09 mg); riboflavin (0.03 mg); niacin (0.8 mg) (AFSUN J., 2018).

Tomatoes play an important role in human diet because they are a good source of minerals and vitamins a remedy for night blindness. Tomatoes contain a high level of lycopene; substances that are used in some of the pricier facial cleansers that are available for purchase (Wang, 2020). Tomatoes also help to prevent several types of cancer. Studies indicate that high levels of lycopene in tomatoes reduce the chances of developing prostate, colorectal and stomach cancer. Lycopene is a natural antioxidant that works effectively to slow the growth of cancerous cells (Bathla, 2019; Labrie & Marcelis; 2020). Tomatoes help maintain strong bones. This is because they contain considerable amounts of calcium and Vitamin K. Both nutrients are essential in strengthening and performing minor repairs on the bones as well as the bone tissue (Amao, 2018).

Plant population is an important agronomic factor that modulates the crop microenvironment and affects the growth, development and yield formation of crops. Within certain limits, an increase of Plant Population Density (PPD) decreases the growth and yield per plant but the reverse occurs for yield per unit area (Hussen, *et al.*, 2013). The effect of plant population on growth, plant characters, and yield could vary due to varietal characters and growing seasons in the same geographical areas. Thus, the relationship of seed yield with different growth parameters and yield components under variable planting density is very important to understand the basic mechanism of the yield-plant density relationship and this would also help in optimizing plant population for improving the yield of tomato. (Rahman & Hossain, 2011). Spacing plays a vital role in the proper growth and development of the plant. Yield is the result of interplant and intra plant competition. Optimum plant spacing utilizes maximum natural resources, such as nutrients, sunlight, soil moisture, etc. and ensures satisfactory yield and proper use of land (Wagayehu, *et al.*, 2015; Abrha, *et al.*, 2015).

The correct spacing for tomato plants depends partly on how they are grown. When stakes are used or tomato cages to support the plants, allow 1.5 to 3 feet of space between plants should be allowed. When grown without support plants should rest on the ground as they grow, with 3 to 4 feet between plants. If planting in rows, allow 3 to 4 feet between rows. In addition, consider planting fast-growing, early-season crops, such as lettuce or spinach, in this space. These plants mature and are ready for harvest before your tomatoes become large enough to overshadow them (Kirimu, *et al.*, 2011).

Tomato is a high yielding vegetable that requires a lot of fertilizers for its proper establishment, growth and yield. However negative effects of chemical fertilizers on the soils and environment have been recognized as one of the limiting factors in sustainable agricultural production (Li, 2018) Chen & Ruan, 2018). Most farmers do not apply fertilizers due to high costs and unreliable availability of inorganic fertilizers. In addition, few farmers who use chemical fertilizers have adequate knowledge on the recommended rates (Dalokom, 2016) leading to application of high amounts of chemical fertilizers hence

causing soil nutrient imbalance. Organic materials such as poultry manure are recognized as suitable organic fertilizer.

Poultry manure if well-handled is the most cherished of all animal manures (Vasilev, 2017). The use of poultry manure for soil fertility maintenance, growth and yield of tomatoes. (Ojeniyi, 2010, Olorode 2020). The amounts of nutrients in poultry manure may differ due to different factors like breed of the birds, litter used, and moisture content of the manure and deity of the birds (Ashworth, (2020). Inorganic fertilizers are expensive and largely out of reach by the small-scale farmers in Uganda. Therefore, it is pertinent to explore the use of organic fertilizers to increase crop production among farmers in Yola. Organic fertilizers such as poultry manure become very good alternative to mineral fertilizer. Azeez (2017) reported that poultry manure if well-handled is the most cherished of all animal manures because it contains all the essential plant nutrients such as phosphorous, nitrogen, potassium, zinc, iron, chlorine, calcium, magnesium, boron, copper, molybdenum and Sulphur which are responsible for the fertilization of the soils. This makes it the most appropriate organic manure for tomato production. Therefore, this study was done to evaluate the effect of Spacing and Poultry Manure on Marketable and Unmarketable fruits of Tomato (*Solanum Lycopersicon L.*)

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum L.*) is one of the most important vegetable crops in Nigeria, widely cultivated for its nutritional, economic, and industrial value. In Adamawa State, tomato farming provides income and serves as a major food component for households. However, tomato production in Yola and other parts of Nigeria is often constrained by low yield and poor fruit quality, particularly the high proportion of unmarketable fruits arising from inadequate soil fertility management, improper plant population density, and poor agronomic practices. Farmers in the Adamawa State typically rely on chemical fertilizers which are expensive, sometimes unavailable, and can degrade soil health over time. Organic manure, when properly applied, has been shown to improve soil structure, nutrient availability, and crop productivity, yet its optimal rate for tomato production in Yola remains poorly established. Similarly, plant spacing plays a critical role in determining fruit set, size, and quality, as overcrowded plants often lead to competition for resources and an increased incidence of pests and diseases, while excessively wide spacing may reduce yield per unit area. Despite the importance of these two factors, little empirical research has been conducted in Yola to establish the combined effects of organic manure application and plant spacing on the proportion of marketable and unmarketable tomato fruits. This gap makes it difficult for farmers to adopt evidence-based practices that would maximize tomato productivity and profitability. Therefore, this study sought to determine the effects of organic manure and plant spacing on marketable and unmarketable fruits of tomato in Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The main aim of the study was to determine the effects of organic manure and spacing on marketable and unmarketable fruits of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum L.*) in Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria, Specifically the study was designed to:

1. Determine the effect of different rates of organic manure on the number and weight of marketable fruits of tomato.
2. Assess the effect of different rates of organic manure on the number and weight of unmarketable fruits of tomato.
3. Examine the effect of plant spacing on the number and weight of marketable fruits of tomato.
4. Evaluate the effect of plant spacing on the number and weight of unmarketable fruits of tomato.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Design

This study adopted a field-based experimental design arranged as a split-plot in a factorial fashion with three replications at Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The experimental factors were: (A) organic manure rate (main-plot factor) and (B) plant spacing (sub-plot factor), using tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) as the test crop. Each replicate (block) contained all treatment combinations, and plots within blocks were randomized separately for main and sub-plots to satisfy the assumptions of the split-plot design.

Experimental Site

The field experiment was conducted at the Teaching and Research farm of the Department of Crop Production and Horticulture, Faculty of Agriculture, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State in Northeast Nigeria. The farm lies between Latitude N 9° 20' 38" and Longitude 12° 30' 51" East of the equator at an altitude 232.3m above sea level. The cropping history of the experimental site was taken; the farm attendant detailed the researcher on the type of crop cultivated on experimental site year before the experiment.

Experimental Layout

The experimental field was prepared by mechanical plowing with the aid of a tractor to ensure a uniform seedbed. The land was then divided into blocks and further sub-divided into plots of equal size for treatment allocation. Each experimental plot measured 2 m × 2 m, with a spacing of 1 m between blocks and 0.5 m between adjacent plots to minimize nutrient and water interference across treatment units. The experiment consisted of nine blocks, and each block was made up of twenty-five plots, giving a total of 225 experimental units.

Planting Materials

The planting materials used for the experiment consisted of three tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) cultivars, namely Tandino, UTC, and Dansiriya, which were sourced from local tomato farmers along the Yola bypass in Adamawa State. These cultivars were selected due to their adaptability and wide acceptance among farmers in the study area. In addition to the planting materials, a range of farm implements and inputs were utilized to facilitate field operations. These included a knapsack sprayer, herbicide, cutlass, local hoe, rake, garden fork, measuring tape, measuring ruler, rope, watering can, and well-decomposed poultry manure used as the organic soil amendment.

Nursery Preparation

Nursery beds were prepared and raised to 15 cm above the ground level to avoid erosion. The seed of all the cultivars that were sown underwent a viability test using the floatation method by (Kelly & Boyham, 2010) to be sure of the viability of the seeds. This was done by putting the seed in a container and pouring water on it to observe all the seeds that float above to be discarded. The seeds also underwent germination tests where ten seeds from each cultivar was sown and observed its germination to be sure of the germination capability of the seeds. The seeds were sown by drilling at 10cm deep and covered with fine sand and some dry grasses. Watering was done twice daily morning and evening by using a watering can to ensure sufficient moisture for seed germination. As soon as the seeds germinate the dry grasses were removed for proper seedlings establishment. Other cultural practices were observed until the seedlings are ready for transplanting.

Transplanting

Tomato seedlings were transplanted to the experimental plots at four weeks after sowing, when they had developed

3 to 4 true leaves, in line with the recommendation of Kisetu and Heri (2014). Transplanting was carried out in the evening hours to minimize the effects of transplanting shock and enhance seedling establishment. Each planting hole received one healthy seedling, ensuring uniform plant density across the experimental plots.

Weed Control

Weeding was done to control weeds to avoid competition for nutrients between the plants and the weeds. The weeding was done manually using local hoe and handpicking. Pest and diseases were controlled by the use of pesticide the reason is that wood ash may affect the treatment which eventually will affect the result of the study. On the event of adverse temperature water was spread around the experiment site to reduce the effect of high temperature on the growing plants. On the event of moisture stress water was sprinkle on the plots using watering can.

Poultry Manure Application

The required quantities of poultry manure were accurately measured using an electric sensitive weighing balance in the Crop Production and Horticulture Laboratory, Faculty of Agriculture, Modibbo Adama University, Yola. The manure was then evenly incorporated into the experimental plots three weeks prior to transplanting to allow adequate decomposition and nutrient mineralization. The treatments consisted of five application rates: $0 t ha^{-1}$ (control), $15 t ha^{-1}$, $20 t ha^{-1}$, $25 t ha^{-1}$, and $30 t ha^{-1}$. Incorporation was done thoroughly into the topsoil to ensure uniform distribution of nutrients across the plots.

Method of Data Collection

Five plants per plot were consecutively selected and tagged for determination of number of marketable and unmarketable fruits which were evaluated after each harvest.

Number of Marketable Fruits

The number of marketable fruits harvested from the 5 selected plants that were free from visible damage, insect pest, diseases and not extra small-size ($>20 g$) were considered as marketable fruits. The fruits were counted at each harvest time, averaged and converted to the number of marketable fruits.

Number of Unmarketable Fruits

Fruits from the 5 selected plants per plot with cracks, rotting, damaged by insects, diseases, birds and sunburn as well as extra small-size ($<20 g$) were counted at each harvest time and expressed in number and were converted to the number of unmarketable fruits.

Method of Data Analysis

The data generated from the research were organized using Microsoft Excel (MS Excel) and then were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SPSS version 22. The differences among the treatment mean for significant result was performed using Least Significant Difference at 0.05 confidence level.

RESULTS

1. Effect of Organic Manure Rates and Plant Spacing on Marketable and Unmarketable Tomato Fruits

Table 1: Mean Effects of Spacing and PM on Number of Marketable fruit of Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L) at first harvest, second harvest and third harvest in 2021, 2022 and 2023 Growing Season

Treatment	First harvest				Second harvest				Third Harvest			
	2021	2022	2023	Comb	2021	2022	2023	Comb	2021	2022	2023	Com
Cultivar												
Tandina	6.061	16.45b	10.680b	10.045b	16.827b	18.65b	16.467b	16.123c	19.187b	18.25b	22.68a	20.32a
UTC	6.800	19.25a	10.973a	11.056a	19.453a	19.39b	19.453a	19.234a	19.640b	19.09b	20.37b	19.34b
Dansiriya	6.480	15.60b	9.749c	9.234c	15.827b	21.49a	15.827b	17.231b	21.867a	20.49a	19.96c	20.43a
P^F	0.234	(0.05)	0.042	0.001	0.002	0.040	0.002	0.001	0.024	0.140	0.001	0.001
PM												
15 tons/ha	6.722b	17.20c	11.556b	6.776a	17.511c	20.80b	17.510	12.828c	21.269b	21.60b	21.29b	14.999e
20 tons/ha	7.129a	17.33c	11.711a	6.881a	17.644c	19.09c	17.634	12.839c	20.333c	20.70c	21.16b	15.203cb
25 tons/ha	7.076a	18.09b	11.444b	6.950a	18.444b	20.49b	18.445b	13.359b	19.444d	18.11d	21.40b	15.623b
30 tons/ha	7.338a	20.09a	11.689a	7.023a	20.333a	23.60a	20.331a	14.557a	23.867a	22.80a	23.16a	17.009a
Control	3.971c	12.80d	5.933c	3.889b	12.911d	15.93d	12.611	9.497d	16.222e	15.09e	18.02c	12.611d
P^F	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.0001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.0001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.0001
Spacing												
90x60 cm	4.473d	14.04c	10.467b	5.629b	15.378c	16.89d	15.313d	11.278d	18.578c	16.25d	18.80d	13.776c
80x40 cm	6.829c	17.00b	10.400b	6.436a	17.000b	20.44b	16.913c	12.371c	20.578b	19.83c	21.02c	15.229b
60x30 cm	6.920b	18.31a	10.356c	6.407a	18.311a	21.31a	18.202a	13.234a	21.311a	22.22a	22.22a	15.858a
50x50 cm	7.089a	18.38a	10.578a	6.556a	18.378a	20.38b	18.338a	13.274a	20.444b	21.51b	21.69b	15.380a
40x20 cm	6.92b	17.78b	10.533a	6.497a	17.778b	20.20c	17.778b	12.915b	20.244b	21.63b	21.29c	15.203b
P^F	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.0001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.0001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.0001

Means values in a column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different by LSD (P<0.05)

Table 1 shows the mean effects of spacing and poultry manure (PM) rates on the number of marketable fruits of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) across the first, second, and third harvests during the 2021, 2022, and 2023 growing seasons. Results indicate that poultry manure application had a significant influence on the number of marketable fruits produced. The highest values were consistently recorded at 30 t ha^{-1} , which produced significantly more marketable fruits across all harvests and years compared to other treatments. This was followed by 25 t ha^{-1} and 20 t ha^{-1} , which also performed better than the control. The control treatment (0 t ha^{-1}) recorded the lowest number of marketable fruits in all seasons and harvests, reflecting the negative effect of nutrient deficiency on fruit yield.

In terms of tomato cultivars, UTC generally produced higher numbers of marketable fruits across most harvests, while Dansiriya and Tandino recorded lower values. For spacing, closer spacings such as 60 × 30 cm and 50 × 50 cm gave significantly higher numbers of marketable fruits compared to wider spacing (90 × 60 cm), indicating that optimum plant population enhanced yield. Overall, the results demonstrate that increasing poultry manure application up to 30 t ha^{-1} , combined with appropriate plant spacing, significantly improved the number and weight of marketable tomato fruits, while control plots without manure consistently produced the least yield. This implies that adequate organic manure not only enhances fruit quantity but also improves quality, thereby reducing the proportion of unmarketable fruits.

2. Effect of Organic Manure Rates and Plant Spacing on Unmarketable and Marketable Tomato Fruits

Table 2: Mean Effects of Spacing and PM on Unmarketable Fruit of Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L) at first harvest, second harvest and third harvest in 2021, 2022 and 2023 Growing Season

Treatment	First harvest				Second harvest				Third Harvest			
	2021	2022	2023	Comb	2021	2022	2023	Comb	2021	2022	2023	Com
Cultivar												
Tandina	1.373b	1.925b	2.075a	1.432c	1.720b	3.161b	1.677b	2.431b	1.933c	3.980b	2.253a	2.543b
UTC	1.467a	2.332a	1.520c	1.543b	1.987a	3.387a	1.987a	2.654a	2.187b	4.347a	2.160b	2.876a
Dansiriya	1.440a	1.763c	1.827b	1.654a	1.613c	2.941c	1.613b	1.564c	2.333a	3.772c	1.867c	2.564b
P^F	0.856	0.208	0.461	0.543	0.495	0.549	0.437	0.056	0.565	0.382	0.029	0.065
PM												
15 tons/ha	1.689b	2.051b	2.044a	2.9778b	1.911a	3.440a	1.911a	4.2074b	2.133c	4.293a	2.022b	5.0074b
20 tons/ha	1.200c	2.031c	1.844b	2.7926b	1.867b	3.229b	1.867b	3.8444c	2.133c	4.122b	2.267a	4.8593b
25 tons/ha	1.289c	2.144a	1.511c	2.9638b	1.910a	3.189c	1.911a	3.6370c	2.422a	4.153b	2.511a	5.0222b
30 tons/ha	1.176a	2.042b	1.800bc	3.6889a	1.844c	3.004c	1.844b	5.0963a	2.378b	4.007bc	1.956c	5.5185a
Control	1.778a	1.764d	1.836b	1.4711c	1.333d	2.971d	1.262c	2.1763d	1.689	3.589c	1.711d	3.7333c
P^F	0.013	0.192	0.461	0.0001	0.045	0.205	0.014	0.001	0.014	0.102	0.044	0.001
Spacing												
90x60 cm	1.978a	1.949c	1.756c	1.9259c	0.711d	3.144a	0.716d	2.1052c	1.222d	3.951b	1.000d	2.8444d
80x40 cm	1.422b	2.080a	1.800b	2.7407b	1.244c	3.202a	1.247c	3.6452c	1.556c	4.089a	1.489c	4.6667c
60x30 cm	1.356b	1.947c	1.933a	3.2000a	1.489c	3.189a	1.489c	4.0963b	1.689c	4.042a	1.778c	5.1418b
50x50 cm	1.089c	2.022b	1.778c	3.0815ba	2.289b	3.107a	2.291b	4.3193b	2.511b	4.007a	2.689b	5.5111b
40x20 cm	1.289c	2.036b	1.769c	2.9452ba	3.133a	3.191a	3.053a	4.7953a	3.778a	4.076a	3.511a	5.9704a
P^F	0.002	0.650	0.235	0.001	0.001	0.839	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.433	0.001	0.001

Means values in a column followed by the same letter(s) are not significantly different by LSD (P<0.05)

Table 2 shows the mean effects of spacing and poultry manure (PM) rates on the number of unmarketable tomato fruits across the first, second, and third harvests during the 2021, 2022, and 2023 growing seasons. The results reveal that both poultry manure application and spacing significantly influenced the production of unmarketable fruits, though the trends varied across years and harvests.

With respect to poultry manure, the control plots (0 t ha^{-1}) generally recorded lower numbers of unmarketable fruits compared to plots treated with higher manure rates. For example, during the first harvest of 2021, the control gave 1.778 unmarketable fruits, while higher manure rates such as 25 and 30 t ha^{-1} produced fewer in that year but significantly higher numbers across combined harvests (e.g., 5.52 at 30 t ha^{-1} in the third harvest combined). This indicates that although poultry manure enhanced total fruit production, it also increased the absolute number of unmarketable fruits, likely because of heavier fruit load and higher competition leading to more undersized or misshapen fruits. However, when considered proportionally against the increase in marketable yield (Table 1), higher manure rates still improved overall fruit quality and profitability.

Among the tomato cultivars, UTC consistently recorded higher numbers of unmarketable fruits compared to Tandina and Dansiriya across most harvests (e.g., 2.332 in 2022 first harvest; 4.347 in 2022 third harvest). Dansiriya generally produced the fewest unmarketable fruits, although it also had lower marketable yields in Table 1, suggesting that varietal differences strongly influenced fruit quality and tolerance to stress.

In terms of spacing, closer plant spacings such as $40 \times 20 \text{ cm}$ and $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}$ produced the highest numbers of unmarketable fruits across most seasons and harvests (e.g., 5.97 at $40 \times 20 \text{ cm}$ in the combined third harvest). In contrast, wider spacing ($90 \times 60 \text{ cm}$) recorded the lowest numbers of unmarketable fruits (e.g., 1.925 in the combined first harvest; 2.84 in the combined third harvest). This suggests that higher plant density increased intra-specific competition, thereby predisposing plants to smaller or malformed fruits classified as unmarketable.

Overall, the results demonstrate that while increasing poultry manure rates improved total yield, it also raised the absolute number of unmarketable fruits, although the proportion of marketable fruits still improved significantly. Similarly, closer spacings tended to increase unmarketable fruits, while wider spacing reduced them, reflecting a trade-off between maximizing yield per unit area and maintaining fruit quality.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

1) Poultry-manure effect

The findings of the study revealed that increasing poultry manure rates generally produced a greater number of unmarketable fruits across harvests and seasons, although the share of saleable fruit remained comparatively acceptable. The findings is in agreement with research showing that heavy organic manuring can increase total fruit production while also changing fruit quality and the incidence of defects when nutrient and water dynamics are altered. Gao et al.'s meta-analysis documented that organic inputs raise yield and many quality metrics but that effects depend on fertilizer rate and soil status (Gao et al., 2023). Luthuli et al. (2024) found that animal-manure extracts alter physico-chemical fruit attributes. Adekiya and Agbede (2017) reported that timing and method of poultry-manure application significantly change nutrient availability, plant uptake and fruit outcomes mechanisms that explain why higher manure rates can increase defective/unsalable fruit if nutrient balance or water uptake is disrupted. Heeb et al. (2006) compared organic vs inorganic nutrient sources and noted trade-offs between quantity and some aspects of quality under different organic regimes, providing further support for the pattern observed here.

2) Cultivar effect

The findings of the study revealed that the UTC accession recorded the highest number of unmarketable fruits, while Dansiriya produced the lowest, suggesting genetic differences in fruit quality under the tested management practices. This observation aligns with earlier studies that emphasized cultivar-based variation in susceptibility to fruit defects and inherent quality traits (Adebayo et al. (2020) reported significant differences in proximate and pigment composition among Nigerian tomato cultivars, which are closely linked with robustness and visual appeal at harvest. Similarly, Maršić et al. (2011) demonstrated that genotype and environmental factors jointly influence quality attributes such as firmness, phenolic content, and other marketability parameters. Carrari and Fernie (2006) further explained that genetic variations in metabolism, cell-wall properties, and stress response mechanisms account for differential susceptibility to physiological disorders and reduced fruit appearance as plants mature. Supporting this, Heeb et al. (2006) found that tomato cultivars respond differently to fertilizer regimes, a result consistent with the cultivar × manure interactions observed in this study.

3) Spacing effect

The findings of the study revealed that tighter planting arrangements (e.g., 40 × 20 cm and 50 × 50 cm) tended to increase the count of rejected fruits, whereas wider configurations (90 × 60 cm) consistently reduced rejects across seasons and harvests. This result is in agreement with several field trials and reviews which have shown that higher plant density amplifies competition for light, water, and nutrients, thereby elevating the incidence of small, cracked, or physiologically damaged fruits. For instance, Getachew et al. (2020) reported that denser tomato populations at closer inter- and intra-row spacings yielded a higher proportion of unmarketable fruits due to intensified resource competition. Similarly, Peet (2009) explained that physiological disorders such as blossom-end rot, sunscald, and uneven ripening are exacerbated under crowded canopies because restricted calcium allocation, irregular water flow, and excessive shading impair fruit development. Supporting this, a University of California Agriculture and Natural Resources (UC ANR, 2018) bulletin emphasized that dense planting alters canopy microclimate, often increasing fruit defects. In addition, trials summarized by Shankar et al. (2013) highlighted that wider spacing improves airflow, reduces disease and pest pressure, and enhances fruit integrity, thus contributing to lower rejection rates. Collectively, these studies reinforce the observation that plant spacing is a critical management factor influencing tomato fruit quality and marketability.

4) Harvest trends

The findings of the study revealed that unmarketable fruit counts generally increased from the first to the third harvest within each season, suggesting that plant senescence and declining nutrient availability contributed to greater rejection rates at later harvest stages. This result aligns with both synthesis and experimental studies indicating that fruit quality often deteriorates over successive pickings as plants age and sink–source dynamics shift. For instance, Arah et al. (2015) emphasized in their mini-review that preharvest management practices—including fertility, irrigation, pruning, and harvest maturity—play a critical role in postharvest quality, and they noted that later harvests frequently exhibit higher rates of physiological disorders and handling losses when nutrients or water become limiting. Similarly, Carrari and Fernie (2006) explained that developmental shifts in ripening, softening, and hormonal regulation predispose later fruits to defects if plant support systems falter. In addition, extension reports and postharvest reviews have documented how cumulative stresses, heightened disease pressure, and natural senescence contribute to elevated cull rates toward the end of the production cycle. Taken together, these studies corroborate the interpretation that plant aging and nutrient depletion substantially increase the incidence of unsalable fruits in later harvests.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that both plant spacing and harvest sequence play a critical role in determining the proportion of marketable versus unmarketable tomato fruits. Tighter plant populations, while maximizing land use, significantly increased fruit rejection due to heightened competition for nutrients, water, and light, which in turn predisposed fruits to physiological disorders and defects. Conversely, wider spacing improved fruit quality and reduced culls by ensuring better resource allocation, airflow, and canopy balance. Furthermore, the progressive increase in unmarketable fruit counts from the first to the third harvest highlights the influence of plant aging, nutrient depletion, and cumulative stress factors on fruit integrity. These results emphasize that optimizing plant density alongside timely harvest and sound agronomic management can substantially minimize losses, enhance fruit quality, and improve overall productivity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Adopt optimal plant spacing: Farmers should avoid excessively tight spacing that increases competition and unmarketable yields. Wider arrangements are recommended to balance land use efficiency with fruit quality.
2. Enhance nutrient and water management: Since nutrient depletion and irregular water flow exacerbate fruit defects, tomato growers should adopt soil fertility programs that replenish nutrients throughout the cropping season, alongside consistent irrigation schedules, to sustain fruit quality across successive harvests.
3. Strengthen canopy and airflow management: Appropriate spacing, pruning, and staking should be practiced to maintain good canopy structure, improve aeration, and reduce physiological disorders and pest/disease pressure.
4. Harvest management strategies: Farmers should implement timely and selective harvesting to reduce physiological stress on aging plants and minimize the accumulation of unmarketable fruits in later harvest cycles.

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